

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the first version of the Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan (DACP) of the Ageing@Work project.

Ageing@Work is a Horizon 2020 project aiming to develop a platform of advanced, personalized and adaptive ICT tools. These tools will help tailoring the workplace to the evolving needs and specificities of the ageing workers, both in terms of ergonomics and in terms of work processes and task assignments. Moreover, the platform along with the toolkit will support the ageing worker's active and healthy ageing at work and at home, focusing on workability, physical and mental health support, flexible management of work and quality of life support.

The document describes the overall awareness raising process, the management and monitoring of the dissemination activities and partners' responsibilities. It includes specific actions and activities that will be carried out by the Ageing@Work consortium members in order to ensure success and maximum publicity for the project and its results. With that said, this deliverable outlines:

1. **What to disseminate** - Chapter two is devoted to the basic project-related information that will be conveyed throughout the project
2. **To whom** – Chapter three consists of the key stakeholder groups that will serve as the main audiences for the project's dissemination, awareness raising and communication campaign
3. **By what means** – Chapter four includes all the channels and tools that will be utilized by project partners in order to successfully implement the dissemination activities
4. **When** – Chapter five provides the time frame in order to ensure that the timing of the dissemination activities is appropriate, during the lifespan of the project and beyond
5. **Monitoring of the process** – Chapter six identifies the indicators to gauge success on the dissemination, awareness raising and communication actions, enabling partners to refine efforts over the course of the project

This deliverable is corresponding to the Task 8.1 “Awareness raising and dissemination strategy” of Work Package (WP) 8 “Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Business Planning”. The DACP will be updated at least once more in June 2020 (M18 of project duration), but ad hoc revisions will also be made, if necessary, according to the progress of the project.

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List of Terms and definitions

Table 1. Definitions.

Abbreviation	Definition
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
DACP	Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan
DoA	Description of Action
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
M	Month
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This report, titled “**D8.1: Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan**” (DACP), aims to design the strategy, plan and activities to be implemented under the Ageing@Work project, with a view to maximizing the project’s visibility and impact. With that in mind, this deliverable outlines the approach to (i) effectively communicate the project and disseminate its results, (ii) guide the partners in planning and implementing their individual dissemination activities and (iii) continuously monitor the efficiency and the timely planning of the actions. With the plans and actions described, the Ageing@Work Consortium aims to meet the following dissemination objectives:

- To effectively promote the project and its outcomes to all possible target groups / audiences in a national and a European level;
- To establish links and liaisons with international organizations and other interested stakeholders in order to provide wider dissemination;
- To establish synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives;
- To validate the project outcomes, in order to obtain feedback from expert groups, scientists and interested user communities.

1.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

The Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan will serve as the basis for the awareness raising and dissemination activities foreseen in Task 8.1. This deliverable will also provide the guidelines for the organisation of the events and workshops of the project as well as for the participation in external events of relevant initiatives that fall under Task 8.2. D8.1 will nurture the ground for the successful exploitation of Ageing@Work’s results, as it will define the project’s main exploitable assets as well as the main stakeholder groups.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

With the above in mind, the “Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan” is structured as follows:

Chapter 1 - Introduction: Provides introductory information with respect to the DACP and its structure as well as its scope and its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables.

Chapter 2 – Dissemination assets: Presents the main project’s assets to be disseminated throughout the period of the grant

Chapter 3 - Target groups: Consists of the key stakeholder groups that will serve as the main audiences for the project's dissemination, awareness raising and communication campaign.

Chapter 4 - Channels and tools: Encompasses all the channels and tools that will be utilized for the dissemination activities of the project, such as the project's web portal, social media accounts etc.

Chapter 5 - Time plan: Provides the time frame for the communication, awareness raising and dissemination activities of the project partners

Chapter 6 -Performance indicators and monitoring: Identifies the indicators to gauge success on the dissemination, awareness raising and communication actions, enabling partners to refine efforts over the course of the project.

Chapter 7 - Conclusions: Pertains the conclusions of the Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan as well as the way forward.

The Annexes include the form of the stakeholders list, the dissemination activities list, the future events list as well as the EU requirements on communication and dissemination of results and finally a template to be used when reporting an event that is organized by a member of the Consortium.

This deliverable will be updated at least once more in M18 providing a more detailed analysis of the dissemination actions and plans as the project evolves and dissemination activities become more meaningful. Ad-hoc revisions might also be made, if considered as necessary, during the project life span.

2. Dissemination assets

The assets / outcomes depicted in Figure 1 will be disseminated by all partners with a view to maximizing the project’s impact and visibility. This information will be conveyed in a meaningful way and tailored to each stakeholder group, in order to promote not only the Ageing@Work’s results, but also its vision and aim.

Figure 1. Dissemination assets.

3. Target groups

The key stakeholders of Ageing@Work can be segmented in the target groups outlined in Table 2 below. The actual stakeholders will be identified and registered in a stakeholders Excel worksheet (ANNEX II) which is devoted to that purpose exactly.

Table 2. Ageing@Work target groups

Target groups
Business stakeholders:
Businesses that may serve as users of the Ageing@Work platform and their personnel including the ageing workers, the Human Resources / Occupational Health and Safety departments, the managers tasked with the design of work environments, the decision-makers such as CEOs, Vice Presidents etc.
Other businesses who may serve as partners / collaborators.
Health and social care service providers, public or private, interested in better managing the monetary and societal costs that are implied by a constantly ageing population.
Insurance providers who can foster and support the adoption of Ageing@Work’s solutions to help improve their insured clients’ health and reduce potential claims in the future.
Academic and research stakeholders:
Academics, researchers and experts focused on advancing the scientific fields cross-cutting Ageing@Work like healthy ageing, active and assisted living, work place innovation etc.
Governmental and policy stakeholders:
EU Institutions and Agencies, such as the EC, the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, the European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions, etc.
National regulators and policy-makers in relevant public authorities.
General public stakeholders
Non-governmental organizations, civil society groups or simply citizens, for example relatives and/or carers of older people, interested in the potential of Ageing@Work to address needs relevant to them.

4. Channels and tools

Several dissemination channels and tools of the Ageing@Work project will be utilized for awareness raising and stakeholder engagement throughout the duration of the project and beyond. These channels and tools are presented in the following list.

1. Graphical identity and promotional material
2. Project's web-portal and partners' web-portals
3. Project's social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) and partners' social media accounts
4. Online newsletter
5. Publications
6. Participation in external events (exhibitions, business events, information days, etc.)
7. Ageing@Work workshops
8. Ageing@Work final conference
9. Synergies with relevant projects/initiatives
10. EU dissemination channels

The dissemination, awareness raising and communication assets of the project will be distributed through the aforementioned channels and tools to all targeted groups. This process will involve all the activities depicted in Figure 2.

All partners will actively participate and contribute to dissemination and stakeholder engagement efforts both at organizational as well as individual level.

Figure 2. Dissemination, awareness raising and communication activities

4.1 Graphical identity and promotional material

The creation of a graphical identity and promotional material is key for enabling the effective dissemination of the project and its activities when needed. Promotional material will be mainly used both at project workshops and external events, where Ageing@Work partners participate. Also, it will be used in the everyday publicity of the project. In compliance with the EU requirements on dissemination of results, as set in Grant Agreement number 826299, Article 29, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic), must display the EU emblem with appropriate prominence and also include the following text: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 826299”*. In applications for protecting results (including patent applications), the following text must be included: *“The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 826299”*. In reports and deliverables of public dissemination level, the following disclaimer must also be included: *“The current report reflects only the author’s view and the Ageing@Work Consortium and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”*. All obligations, requirements and consequences of no-compliance stated in the Grant Agreement can be found in Annex I.

With that in mind, the main promotional material of the Ageing@Work project is described in the following sub-sections. Each partner will be responsible for translations (if considered necessary) and printing of the material according to its specific needs. **Partners should not produce any kind of promotional material, related to the project, without the previous review and approval of WP8 leader Q-PLAN.**

4.1.1 Logos

Ageing@Work’s logo was developed in the beginning of the project (M1) and has been approved by all partners.

Figure 3. Ageing@Work's logo

4.1.2 Leaflets and posters

A project leaflet and a poster presenting general information on the project (aim, objectives, partners, etc.) will be created by M4 of the project. Apart from the general project leaflet and posters, specific printable promotional material for the promotion of Ageing@Work's events and pilot schemes will be prepared during the project, according to the needs of the responsible partners.

4.1.3 Templates

Templates have been created for the consortium partners to be able to produce their project deliverables and their presentations. In particular, a template for the project's deliverables as well as a template for the partners' presentations have been created and made available to project partners.

4.1.4 Videos

A short video presenting Ageing@Work project will be produced so as not only to create awareness but also to efficiently boost the dissemination activities. The video will emphasize on promoting the project's results along with their value propositions as well as its events and demonstration activities. The preparation of the video is the responsibility of Q-PLAN. The video will be uploaded onto the YouTube channel of the project, that has been already created in M2 of the project (February 2019).

4.2 Ageing@Work's web portal and partners' web portals

The project's web portal (<https://ageingatwork-project.eu/>) has already been developed by M2 of the project (February 2019) and it constitutes the main gateway to Ageing@Work's activities, deliverables, news and events. At this point the web portal contains information about the project's concept and approach, its objectives, the consortium, the most recent and active related projects as well as some initial news. As the project evolves, the web portal will be further enriched with all publishable deliverables, promotional material and events. Links to relevant initiatives, to social media accounts of the project and to project partner's webpages are also included.

The news section of the Ageing@Work's web-portal will be updated at least once in a month and will be available for at least five years after the period of the grant. The web-portal will also be equipped with an online subscription tool for visitors.

Q-PLAN is responsible for the design, operation and update of the project's web-portal. All partners are required to create links to the project web-portal on their websites and to contribute with the news to be uploaded as well as to publish occasionally news of the project to the web-portals of their organizations. The Ageing@Work's portal will be mentioned in all publicity material generated by the project Consortium.

4.3 Social media networks

The creation of a Facebook page, a LinkedIn page, a Twitter account and a YouTube channel is considered as an enabling key to the communication of the project’s news, events and outcomes. To this end, all social media accounts have been created in M2 of the project (February 2019) as depicted in Table 3.

Table 3. Social media accounts

Social media platform	Ageing@Work’s URL
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Ageingatwork-project-434374127300138/
Twitter	https://twitter.com/AgeingWorkproj1
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ageing-work-project/
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCJsxLGgNFnLi0e6B-FsK8bQ/

The project’s social media will be continuously updated in English with news about the project’s activities and results, various events, scientific news, news from several organizations / associations that promote healthy and productive ageing, news from related EU projects etc. The frequency of social media posts will depend on the availability of news about the activities and results of the project. Regarding the YouTube channel, a promotional video will be produced so as not only to create awareness but also to exploit viral marketing effects. The video will be uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel and emphasize on promoting the project’s results along with their value propositions as well as its events and demonstration activities.

Q-PLAN is responsible for the administration of the Ageing@Work’s social media sites. All partners are required to become member or/and follower of the social media accounts, to actively like the social media posts of the project and also to disseminate publishable material through their personal networks. Partners are also asked to interact with news, uploads, tweets and retweets, conversations and likes in the social media sites of the project, during the whole three-years duration of the grant, as well as to publish posts and news about Ageing@Work regularly, through the social media of their organizations.

4.4 Online newsletter and targeted recipients’ mailing list

An online newsletter will be prepared and distributed through MailChimp, presenting among others the achieved results, upcoming activities and events, news from similar initiatives and news in the relevant scientific fields. The frequency of newsletter issues will depend on the amount and importance of news to be presented, with the target to produce a newsletter at least every 6 months, however additional ad-hoc newsletters may be added if deemed necessary.

The initial recipients' list will be created and administered by Q-PLAN, based on desk research and existent dissemination databases. The list will be continuously updated during the project, therefore everyone who is interested will be able to subscribe to the recipients' list by registering on the newsletter section of the project's website or unsubscribe, according to GDPR rules. The recipients' list may also be used for the dissemination of other news and announcements related to the project activities.

The newsletter issues will be prepared by Q-PLAN, with the contribution of all partners regarding the content. The content of each issue will be decided and agreed among the consortium. Partners are also required to disseminate the newsletter issues through their own dissemination channels.

4.5 Publications

All partners will contribute to the online fora with scientific (articles in scientific journals / conferences) and non-scientific (press releases, magazine articles, blogs) publications. Scientific knowledge generated during the project will be shared in open access scientific conferences and journals. All partners are responsible for identifying any publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure publications of project assets. All partners do not have the same capacity regarding publications, therefore each partner will undertake the kind of publication (scientific or non-scientific) that is deemed as more suitable. Each partner will make effort to publish in the highest quality appropriate publication, which not only reflects on the Consortiums' reputation but also on the Ageing@Work's initiative. All publications must cite or/and refer to the EU contribution and project grant agreement number, as required in the Article 29 of the Grant Agreement no 826299. The requirements for scientific publications are available in Annex I. All peer reviewed publications will be in open access according to the ["Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020"](#). The first sheet of the "Ageing@Work_dissemination_activities.xls" table, named "Publications" will be used for keeping track of completed publications. The form of the document is shown in Annex III.

4.6 Participation in external events

The partners of the Ageing@Work consortium will participate in several external events with the aim to boost the dissemination of project's activities and results. The targeted events, both scientific and business, will relate to the knowledge fields of the project, the sectors it covers as well as the interests of the project's primary stakeholders. The goal is to keep in touch with the latest advances in the research and industry across Europe, share knowledge with respective communities, and establish contacts and interactions with key stakeholders, while at the same time communicating the results of the project. Partners participating in external events (exhibitions, business events, information days, scientific events and conferences) should disseminate the Ageing@Work project following the guidelines below:

- Before the event, it is necessary to complete "Ageing@Work_future_events.xls" with the required information about the event. The table can be found in Annex IV.
- If a partner is making a presentation, it is requested to use the general project presentation with any modifications necessary to this file, keeping the same template.

- During the event, it is important to disseminate the project's promotional material (leaflets, posters etc.).
- A number of photos must be taken.
- The partner is requested to update the Dissemination and Communication Manager about the participation in the event and to share the photos taken, not later than ten days after the event.
- All partners are asked to complete the second sheet of the "Ageing@Work_dissemination_activities.xls", named "External Events" with all required information about the participation in the event at the latest three weeks after the event. The table can be found in Annex III.

All activities implemented towards the participation of external events as well as their results will be reported in the "Ageing@Work Communication and Dissemination Activities report" D8.4 and updated version, D8.8.

4.7 Ageing@Work's workshops and demonstration/training sessions

During the project, three workshops will take place. The first workshop aims to familiarize all interested parties with the project and platform and to obtain insights from relevant stakeholders and feed them into the Ageing@Work platform and it will be organized by Q-PLAN until M6. The two rest workshops will be realized along with the pilots, by SIEMENS and ANEFA respectively, including parallel demonstration/training sessions, so as to showcase the project's benefits, gather end-user feedback for further improvements, as well as to investigate the interest for the commercial exploitation of the Ageing@Work solution. Local dissemination campaigns for the workshops will be under the responsibility of the organizer partner, with the support of Q-PLAN for central level dissemination (project web-portal and social media, newsletter and massive e-mail sender tool for dispatch of invitations, press release in English, and promotional material in English). All activities implemented under those workshops as well as their results will be reported in the "Ageing@Work Communication and Dissemination Activities report" (deliverables D8.4 and updated version D8.8).

4.8 Ageing@Work's final conference

By the end of the project, a closing event will take place, organized by all project partners under the lead of UPM. The event will probably be organized as satellite event at a larger international event and it will include networking sessions about the future research and challenges in the field. The aim of the conference will be to spread the accumulated knowledge and present the final achievements to scientists, industry, health care providers, insurance companies, policy makers and generally to all interested parties, with a view to fostering policy impact and industry, research and societal use of the project results. Ageing@Work's partners should contribute to further disseminate the final event through their personal networks. All activities implemented towards the organization of this conference will be reported in the second version of the "Ageing@Work Communication and Dissemination Activities report" (deliverable D8.8).

4.9 Synergies with relevant projects /initiatives

Synergies with other relevant EU-funded or international research projects and initiatives will be pursued by all partners in project's research domains and industry sectors to facilitate knowledge interchange, to gain mutual dissemination benefits and to exploit potential cooperation. Possible synergies may comprise the inclusion of the project's web-portal and social media as links in websites and social media of other projects, participation in events of similar projects, dissemination of Ageing@Work's promotional material in events of similar projects, invitations to participate in Ageing@Work's events and exchange of news through each projects' channels. A "Relevant initiatives" sheet has already been created by Q-PLAN and is part of the "Ageing@Work_dissemination_activities.xls" document. The form of this document can be found in Annex III. Project partners should keep track of all similar projects and initiatives, which might be interested in collaboration and should regularly enrich the list. All partners should keep in mind that the Ageing@Work dissemination strategy cannot reach its full potential unless meaningful collaboration with related projects is established.

4.10 EU dissemination channels

The following EU dissemination channels are going to be used during the project:

- **EU-OSHA.** The European Agency for Safety and Health at Work and the Ageing@Work project have some common topics of focus with like musculoskeletal disorders, stress and psychosocial risks at work, developments in ICT and digitalization of work etc.
- **Eurofound.** The European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions is a European Union Agency, whose role is to assist in the development of better social, employment and work-related policies.
- **CEDEFOP.** The European Center for the Development of Vocational Training brings together policy-makers, social partners, researchers and practitioners to share ideas and debate the best ways to improve vocational education and training policies
- **Health National Contact Points (NCPs) network.** National Contact Points provide guidance, practical information, networking and assistance on all aspects of participation in HORIZON 2020.
- **European Enterprise Network (EEN).** The EEN is an EU network of around 600 business support organizations from more than 60 countries, including chambers of commerce and industry, technology centers, research institutes and development agencies.
- **CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service) WIRE.** CORDIS WIRE is a CORDIS online service that helps research and business community to promote projects' activities by publishing news and events on CORDIS
- **EU Info-days, workshops and conferences**

The Project Officer will be contacted with regards to possible dissemination steps supported by the EU.

5. Publicity timetable

Table 4. Publicity timetable

Activity	Responsible partner	Related Work Packages	2019						2020						2021				
			January - February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December	January - February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December	January - February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October
Development of promotional material																			
Logo	CERTH	WP8																	
Template	CERTH	All WPs																	
Presentation	CERTH	All WPs																	
Leaflet, poster	Q-PLAN	WP8																	
Video	Q-PLAN	WP8																	
Web portal																			
Development and operation of project’s web portal	Q-PLAN	WP8																	
Publicity through project’s web portal	All partners	All WP																	
Publicity through partners’ web portals	All partners	All WP																	
Social media networks																			
Creation of social media accounts	Q-PLAN	WP8																	
Publicity through projects’ social media	All partners	All WP																	
Publicity through partners’ social media	All partners	All WP																	
Publicity through YouTube channel of the project	Q-PLAN	WP8																	

Activity	Responsible partner	Related Work Packages	2019						2020						2021				
			January - February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December	January - February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December	January - February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October
Online Newsletter																			
Recipients list creation and update	Q-PLAN	WP8																	
E - newsletter	Q-PLAN	WP8																	
Publications																			
Non – scientific (press releases, blogging)	All partners	WP2-WP8																	
Scientific publications	All partners	WP2-WP8																	
External events																			
Exhibitions, business events, information days etc.	All partners	WP8																	
Scientific events, conferences etc.	All partners	WP8																	
Project's workshops																			
1 st Workshop	Q-PLAN, all partners	WP7, WP8																	
2 nd Workshop	SIEMENS/ANEFA, all partners	WP7, WP8																	
3 rd Workshop	SIEMENS/ANEFA, all partners	WP7, WP8																	
Final conference																			
Project's closing event	All partners	All WPs																	

Activity	Responsible partner	Related Work Packages	2019						2020						2021					
			January - February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December	January - February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December	January - February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December
Synergies with related projects/initiatives																				
Inclusion in other projects web portals, participation in other projects' events, invitations to participate in Ageing@Work's events, co-dissemination, exchange of news etc.	Q-PLAN, all partners	WP8																		
EU dissemination channels																				
EU-OSHA, Eurofound, Cedefop, NCPs network, EEN network, Cordis wire, EU info-days/workshops	Q-PLAN	WP8																		

Beyond the end of the project, partners are committed to continue disseminating the project's outcomes through their everyday activities, networks and means communication employed to reach related stakeholder groups. The stakeholders that will have participated in the activities of the project are expected to act as multipliers of the Ageing@Work's results beyond its lifespan.

6. Performance indicators and monitoring

To measure the success of Ageing@Work’s awareness raising and communication strategy, the following KPIs will be employed and all dissemination activities will be monitored with their results being compared to the KPIs so as to assess whether Ageing@Work is on the right path or if increased dissemination efforts need to take place.

Table 5. KPIs and target values

Indicator (KPI)	Target Value (impact)
Number of scientific papers published	18 (in scientific conferences and journals)
Number of external events / conferences attended	30 events / conferences (research and industrial)
Synergies with major initiatives and networks	10 joint actions
Number of visits to the Ageing@Work web-portal	15,000 unique visitors by the end of the project
Number of followers in the social media accounts	2,000 followers (Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube and Twitter)
Number of promotional material distributed	2,000 copies distributed in project/external events
Number of newsletters	6 newsletters (one per semester)
Number of workshops / participants in each one	3 workshops / 30 participants per workshop
Number of participants in the Final Conference	100 participants (academia, industry and government)

To meet these target values, project partners are expected to continuously carry out publicity actions and also continuously report all publicity and communications outcomes. Q-PLAN will be overall responsible for the monitoring and evaluation of Ageing@Work’s dissemination activities.

Reporting of any dissemination activity and publication is expected from partners by completing the “Ageing@Works_dissemination_activities.xls” document and sending it to WP8 leader Q-PLAN, at the latest three weeks after the dissemination activity or publication. Especially for participation in external events, partners should follow the respective guidelines. In the case of events organized by the project, the partner responsible for the organization of the event must prepare an Event Report, in the form of Annex V, at the latest three weeks after the dissemination activity or publication.

Partners should produce no kind of promotional material related to the project without the previous review and approval of WP8 leader Q-PLAN. Each project partner should immediately contact Q-PLAN if they identify opportunities, problems or risks arising while planning or implementing publicity actions.

7. Conclusions

This document, titled “Dissemination, Awareness raising and Communication Plan”, provided the framework and guidelines for the successful implementation of dissemination, awareness raising and communication activities throughout the lifespan of the project and beyond. As the project evolves, this document will be updated and refined in order to provide a more detailed analysis of the dissemination actions and plans. The actions and plans of this deliverable answer to the following questions:

- What to disseminate?
- To whom?
- By what means?
- When?

This document also provides the monitoring mechanism of the dissemination activities, which is based on targeted KPIs. By communicating the project’s tangible and intangible assets through the most effective channels and tools to timely reach the targeted groups, Ageing@Work will be able to not only go beyond these ambitious KPIs but most importantly to lay the foundations for the successful rollout, replication and thus sustainability of its outcomes.

Annexes

Annex I – EU requirements

ARTICLE 29 of GA 826299— DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS — OPEN ACCESS — VISIBILITY OF EU FUNDING

29.1 Obligation to disseminate results

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium). This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may — under certain conditions (see Article 26.4.1)— need to formally notify the Commission before dissemination takes place.

29.2 Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

(a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

(b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:

(i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or

(ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

(c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

29.3 Open access to research data

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action (**‘data’**), the beneficiaries must:

(a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:

- (i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible;
- (ii) not applicable;
- (iii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the ‘data management plan’ (see Annex 1 of Grant Agreement no 826299);

(b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data under Point (a)(i) and (iii), if the achievement of the action's main objective (as described in Annex 1 of Grant Agreement no 826299) would be jeopardized by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.

29.4 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 826299”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission. This does not however give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

29.5 Disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

29.6 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43). Such a breach may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

Annex V – Events report (template)

Event name

Date

Venue

Ageing@Work

Event report

Project Acronym:	Ageing@Work
Project Full Name:	Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability
Grant Agreement:	No 826299
Project Duration:	3 years (starting 1 January 2019)
Project Coordinator	Dr. Konstantinos Votis
Project URL	https://ageingatwork-project.eu/

Event Organizing Partner		
Responsible author	Author 1	Email:
	Partner:	Phone:

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